

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

6th ENES HPC workshop in Hamburg

Deliverable D6.3

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About this document

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The deliverable is a workshop – see the full list of organisers in the text

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Content

1. Abstract /publishable summary.....	4
2. Conclusion & Results.....	4
3. Project objectives.....	4
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	5
5. References (<i>Bibliography</i>).....	8
6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	8
7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC.....	8
8. Sustainability.....	8
9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results.....	9
10. Appendix: Agenda of the 6 th ENES HPC workshop	11

1. Abstract /publishable summary

The 6th ENES HPC workshop for climate and weather was hosted as a virtual event by DKRZ during the week from May 25th to May 29th, 2020. The series of ENES HPC workshops is being organised by the “ENES HPC-Task Force” with workshops taking place roughly every two years. Based on previous ENES HPC workshops in Lecce (2011 & 2018), Toulouse (2013 & 2016) and Hamburg (2014), this year’s event had originally been planned as an on-site event for about 100 participants.

Finally, the (now virtual) workshop brought together over 180 scientists from the fields of earth system modelling, informing them about the latest developments in high performance computing (HPC) and fostering a mutual exchange, also involving HPC experts. Talks were structured in four sessions focusing on:

“Very high-resolution modelling”, “Performance portability”, “Machine learning for parameterisation schemes” and “Challenges in exascale data processing and visualisation”.

2. Conclusion & Results

The workshop provided a very good overview of state-of-the-art climate and weather models, focusing on storm-resolving configurations and frontier simulations with these models. With the event shifted from physical to virtual, the number of participants increased and the workshop was accessible to a broader audience, namely over 180 participants from 12 European countries, the United States, China, Japan and India. Moreover, the carbon footprint of the event was drastically reduced due to the virtual format that required neither travel nor accommodation for the participants. While the presentations and the associated discussion rounds were very successful, the event lacked the side-discussions and the exchange that are typically an important part of on-site meetings. New ideas might be needed to foster mutual exchange and networking among the participants to make future low-emission events, i.e. virtual conferences and workshops, even more useful and beneficial.

This deliverable includes a short report on the four workshop sessions, the workshop agenda and a link to the abstracts and presentation slides that have been approved for publication by the respective authors.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	YES
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	YES

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	YES
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	YES
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	YES
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	NO
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	NO
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	NO

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The program committee of the 6th ENES HPC workshop consisted of Joachim Biercamp, Dela Spickermann and Florian Ziemen (all DKRZ), who were in charge of organising and hosting the event, and of Daniel Klocke (DWD), Sophie Valcke and Jean-Claude André (CERFACS), Mario Acosta and Kim Serradell (BSC), Reinhard Budich (MPI-M), Peter Dueben (ECMWF), Sandro Fiore (CMCC) and Niklas Röber (DKRZ).

The workshop saw 35 talks by international speakers structured into four sessions. The full agenda is attached to this report.

Session I: Very high-resolution modelling

The first session had eight talks on the topic of very high-resolution modelling. Global storm- and ocean eddy-resolving simulations are not only possible, but reality on relative short time scales. The speakers shared first experiences from this new class of earth system models. Expectations for the advancement of climate science and society were formulated for climate scale integrations with these models. Talks focused on the challenges ahead to make best use of available resources and promising insights from first simulations. Two talks presented evaluations of simulations with storm-resolving models focusing on convection. Meso-scale convective systems were discussed, as an aspect that high-resolution models will simulate better than traditional climate models, and tropopause layer cirrus clouds, where also the very high-resolution models will depend on parameterisations.

To unlock the full potential of the very high-resolution models, they need to run efficiently on current supercomputers. Several speakers presented progress in making existing ocean and atmosphere models more efficient. Methods discussed included (i) refining unstructured meshes to increase the horizontal resolution in regions which benefit most from it, (ii) lowering the precision in parts of the code where there is little benefit from high precision, or (iii) regionally embedding large-eddy resolving models in coarser models to improve the representation of physical processes.

The session showed that very high-resolution climate modelling has been significantly advancing due to the cooperation in Europe. A measure to help sustaining and intensifying these efforts could be a “European Centre for Earth System Science” as a permanently funded institution.

Session II: Performance portability

Session 2 was dedicated to performance portability across emerging computing technologies for weather and climate applications. With 13 talks, session 2 was the longest session of the workshop. It included different high performance computing topics related to cutting-edge hardware and software, such as the first exascale machines planned for the next few years; or novel developments to take advantage of these new technologies efficiently. Moreover, new tools were presented, which promise a revolution in the way of coding numerical models in the future, separating science and computing, making efficient use of the new technologies and heterogeneously taking advantage of both traditional general-purpose and accelerator architectures, all transparent to the user.

Regarding exascale plans, Satoshi Matsuoka (RIKEN) gave more details about Fugaku, the first exascale machine to be deployed; or Peter Bauer (ECMWF) about ECMWF’s roadmap towards extreme-scale computing. New approaches for GPUs were given by Christian Guzman (BSC) using a multi-cells block processing for chemistry solvers, or Johann Dahm (Vulcan Inc.) for a compiler toolchain using FV3. New alternatives or details about tools in development for decoupling numerical modelling and computing were given, too. On this topic, we found different talks about the OpenArray library by Xiaomeng Huang (Tsinghua University); PsyClone by Rupert Ford (STFC Hartree Centre); LFRic by Iva Kavcic (MetOffice) about different alternatives based in ocean and weather cases, which can also be adapted for different hardware at the same time. Additionally, Harald Koestler (Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg); or the use of triangular grids for weather and climate models by Matthias Röthlin (MeteoSwiss) presented new alternatives for code generation. Finally, new alternatives for software development were presented during the session. Robert Jacob (Argonne National Laboratory) spoke about new developments for performance in the Energy Exascale Earth System Model. Piotr Bartman (Jagiellonian University) presented new possibilities using Numba and other approaches for Python, and Dom Heinzeller (CU&NOAA) introduced the Common Community Physics Package (CCPP), a shared infrastructure for model physics.

Session III: Machine learning for parameterisation schemes

The eight talks in session three discussed “Machine learning for parameterisation schemes”. The potential for the application of machine learning techniques in Earth System modelling has improved greatly in recent years as the amount of data that is available for training, the computational power that can be used for training and inference, and the knowledge how to build efficient machine learning tools to emulate very complex non-linear systems has exploded.

The session had several contributions that discussed the emulation of existing parameterisation schemes by neural networks to improve efficiency of the schemes as well as portability to heterogeneous hardware, including the talks by Chris Bretherton (University of Washington), Matthew Chantry (University of Oxford) and Peter Dueben (ECMWF) for, respectively, cloud physics, gravity wave drag and radiation emulation. However, in principle, parameterisation schemes, or at least physical relationships, can also be learned from observations, for example from tower measurements as presented in one of the examples by Richard Loft (University Corporation for Atmospheric Research). The session also covered talks that summarised wider machine learning developments in the Earth System modelling community, including a summary of efforts by NCAR from Richard Loft, NVIDIA from Stan Posey, and ECMWF from Peter Dueben. Further talks covered the importance of interpretable machine learning by Maria Moreno de Castro (DKRZ), the potential to improve predictions of local precipitation by Carlos Gomez (BSC) and the potential for the use of objective uncertainty quantification by Fredrik Jansson (CWI).

Session IV: Challenges in exascale data processing and visualisation

Current climate models, implemented with a higher systems complexity that is paired with an increased resolution, produce larger and larger data sets that need to be analysed, displayed and understood. The last session addressed the associated challenges in exascale data processing and visualisation in the climate and weather domain. With six talks, this session focused on several scientific data management topics at scale, such as, among others, data storage, access, compression, but also data analytics, processing and visualisation.

The first talk by Niklas Röber (DKRZ) focused on the results related to the in situ analysis and visualisation activities on large data collections, performed at DKRZ. The talk also highlighted the relevance of progressive rendering approaches in combination with compression techniques and the use of HPC resources to manage data at such scale. Donatello Elia (CMCC) presented a High Performance Data Analytics-enabled environment for scalable climate data analysis at CMCC based on the Ophidia HPDA framework. The talk also highlighted the weak and strong scalability results of a benchmark on Ophidia, performed using the core hours awarded by PRACE (Call 18), in the context of the ESIWACE CoE, on MareNostrum 4 at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). Valerio Pascucci (University of Utah) presented a talk on data analytics and visualisation of massive climate and weather data with the ViSUS framework and the PIDX library. The link with the Earth System Grid Federation compute service, to effectively deliver visualisation capabilities to the end users through the ESGF data distribution network, was a relevant outcome. Two talks from Julian Kunkel (University of Reading) and Jeff Durachta (NOAA GFDL) focused on I/O aspects like smart I/O scheduling but also on optimised I/O access to data storages to deliver in-flight post processing capabilities in the context of large end-to-end simulation workflows in a data-center like environment. The technologies to address I/O challenges (i.e. RDMA + NVMe oF, ESDM) were also presented. Finally, Aparna Radhakrishnan (Princeton University/NOAA GFDL) described the building blocks for exascale computing at GFDL, from the GFDL Unified Data Archive to the Cloud optimised containerised workflow covering the data, metadata and computing aspect. She also highlighted data exploration examples based on XArray and Dask, as well as some benchmarks.

Information on workshop participation¹

- 183 participants registered in total, 19% of them speakers
 - 20% of registered attendees were female, 11% of the speakers
 - Approx. 20% of registered attendees affiliated with ESIWACE2, 30% of the speakers
 - Attendees from 12 European countries, the USA, China, India and Japan
 - 88% from European institutes, 9% from the US, 3% from Asia
 - 6 participants affiliated with the HPC industry

- 168 connected in GoToMeeting with names displayed:
 - 63 attended on all 4 days
 - 24 attended on 3 days
 - 37 attended on 2 days
 - 44 attended on 1 day only

5. References (*Bibliography*)

None

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Due to the situation with COVID-19, the event was changed into a virtual conference.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

By exchanging knowledge within Europe and bringing in additional information through talks by leading international experts, the workshop increased the capacity of European weather and climate modellers to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems and to prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.

8. Sustainability

This workshop was already the sixth in a series with increasing number of participants. The 7th ENES HPC workshop is already scheduled for 2022 and will be organised by BSC in Barcelona in the framework of the H2020 project IS-ENES3.

8.1 Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date:

See the considerations in sections 2 and 4.

¹ as far as discernible from registration data and names provided

8.2: Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects:

By hosting the workshop as a virtual event, we gained experience and valuable insights on best practices. Those were taken up by WP2 for organising and hosting the ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling on June 30, 2020, which contributes to deliverable D2.6.

The talks on new programming paradigms, in particular domain specific languages, emphasised the close cooperation of ESiWACE with the ESCAPE-2 project in this domain.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The event was widely announced to the target audience and well received as can be seen by the large number of participants. The slides of all presentation were available for download for all registered participants until June 30, 2020. We have asked the speakers for their permission to publish their abstracts and (potentially modified) versions of their slides on the ESiWACE website at: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/6th-hpc-workshop/presentations>

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Organisation of a workshop	Virtual 6th ENES workshop on High Performance Computing for Climate and Weather	25-26 and 28-29 May, 2020	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/6th-hpc-workshop/6th-hpc-workshop/presentations	300

Deliverable D6.3 ESIWACE2 Project

Peer-reviewed articles

None

Publications in preparation OR submitted

None

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable

10. Appendix: Agenda of the 6th ENES HPC workshop

6th ENES HPC Workshop 2020

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CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER
AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

- Session 1: Very high resolution modeling and challenges
- Session 2: Performance portability
- Session 3: Machine learning for parametrization schemes
- Session 4: Data / high volume data analysis

Monday, 25 May 2020

16:00	Welcome & introduction	Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ)	00:15						time lag [hrs]	+ / -	local time speaker
16:15 talk	Sam	Hatfield	ECMWF	00:20	Mixed-precision ocean modelling at ECMWF				01:00	-	15:15
16:35 talk	Nikolay	Koldunov	MARUM/AWI	00:20	Very high resolution modelling with unstructured mesh global ocean model (FESOM2)				00:00	+	16:35
16:55 talk	Gijs	van den Oord	Netherlands eScience Center	00:20	Regional Superparametrization of OpenIFS by 3D LES				00:00	+	16:55
17:15 talk	Miguel	Castrillo	BSC	00:20	The NEMO ORCA36 configuration and approaches to increase NEMO4 efficiency				00:00	+	17:15
17:35	Coffee break										
17:50 talk	Bjorn	Stevens	MPI-M	00:20	Next Generation Earth System Models: Lessons learned and looming challenges				00:00	+	17:50
18:10 talk	Clément	Bricaud	Mercator Ocean International	00:20	Overview of the first year of the NEMO global 1/36° configuration (ORCA36) development				00:00	+	18:10
18:30 talk	Jacqueline	Nugent	University of Washington	00:20	Evaluating Convection and Tropical Tropopause Layer Cirrus in the DYAMOND Simulations				09:00	-	09:30
18:50	End										

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Tuesday, 26 May 2020

09:00	Welcome & introduction	Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ)	00:10		
	Session	Very high-resolution modeling	Florian Ziemer + Daniel Klocke		
09:10 talk	Puxi Li	Chinese Academy of Meteorological Sciences, China	00:20	Model performance of storm resolving models in simulating mesoscale convective systems	time lag [hrs] 06:00 + local time speaker 15:10
	Session	Performance portability	Reinhard Budich + Mario Acosta		
09:30 talk	Satoshi Matsuoka	Riken	00:20	Fugaku.: the First Exascale Machine	time lag [hrs] 07:00 + local time speaker 16:30
09:50 talk	Xiaomeng Huang	Tsinghua University	00:20	OpenArray v1.0: a simple operator library for the decoupling of ocean modeling and parallel computing	time lag [hrs] 06:00 + local time speaker 15:50
10:10 talk	Christian Guzman	BSC	00:20	Accelerating Chemistry Modules in Atmospheric Models using GPUs	time lag [hrs] 00:00 + local time speaker 10:10
10:30 talk	Piotr Bartman	Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Poland	00:20	Bridging performance and pythonicity with Numba, Pythran and ThrustRTC	time lag [hrs] 00:00 + local time speaker 10:30
10:50	Coffee break		00:15		
11:05 talk	Matthias Röthlin	MeteoSwiss	00:20	Preparing dawn for Weather and Climate Models on Triangular Grids	time lag [hrs] 00:00 + local time speaker 11:05
11:25 talk	Harald Koestler	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	00:20	Code Generation Technology for Climate Models	time lag [hrs] 00:00 + local time speaker 11:25
11:45 talk	Rupert Ford	STFC Hartree Centre	00:20	Recent Advances in PSyclone	time lag [hrs] 01:00 - local time speaker 10:45
12:05 talk	Iva Kavcic	MetOffice	00:20	LFRic approach to performance portability	time lag [hrs] 01:00 - local time speaker 11:05
12:25	End		02:55		

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Thursday, 28 May 2020

16:30	Welcome & introduction	Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ)	00:10				time lag [hrs]	'+ / - local time speaker
16:40	talk	Robert Jacob	Argonne National Laboratory	00:20	Software development for performance in the Energy Exascale Earth System Model		07:00 -	09:40
17:00	talk	Peter Bauer	ECMWF	00:20	ECMWF's roadmap towards extreme-scale computing		01:00 -	16:00
17:20	talk	Daniel Arevalo	US NRL	00:20	Computational Evaluation of Commercial Cloud HPC with a Global Atmospheric Model		09:00 -	08:20
17:40	talk	Dom Heinzeller	CU/CIRES & NOAA/ESRL/GSD	00:20	The Common Community Physics Package (CCPP): a shared infrastructure for model physics for operations and research		08:00 -	09:40
18:00	talk	Johann Dahm	Vulcan Inc.	00:20	Compiler toolchain for scalable weather and climate simulation using FV3 on GPUs		09:00 -	09:00
18:20	Coffee break			00:15				
	Machine learning for parametrization schemes	Jean-Claude Andre + Peter Dueben						
18:35	talk	Richard Loft	University Corporation for Atmospheric Research	00:20	Exascale Climate: Can OpenACC and Machine Learning Deliver the Goods?		08:00 -	10:35
18:55	talk	Chris Bretherton	University of Washington	00:20	Deep learning for cloud parameterization schemes		09:00 -	09:55
19:15	talk	Stan Posey	NVIDIA	00:20	GPU Developments for Applications in Climate and Weather		09:00 -	10:15
19:35	talk	Peter Dueben	ECMWF	00:20	Machine learning at ECMWF		01:00 -	18:35
19:55	End			03:15				

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Friday, 29 May 2020

15:00	Welcome & introduction	Joachim Biercamp (DKRZ)	00:10				time lag [hrs]	'+ / - local time speaker
15:10 talk	Machine learning for parameterization schemes	Jean-Claude Andre + Peter Dueben	00:20	Emulation of the gravity wave drag			01:00 -	14:10
15:30 talk	Matthew Chantry	U. Oxford	00:20	Interpretable Machine Learning			00:00 +	15:30
15:50 talk	Maria Moreno de Castro	DKRZ	00:20	Learning to simulate precipitation with Deep Neural Networks			00:00 +	15:50
16:10 talk	Carlos Gomez	BSC	00:20	Uncertainty quantification of atmospheric models - applying the EasyVUQ framework on the DALES model			00:00 +	16:10
16:30 talk	Fredrik Jansson	CWI						
16:50	Niklas Röber	DKRZ	00:20	Large Data Visualization			00:00 +	16:30
17:05 talk	Challenges in exascale data processing and visualization	Niklas Röber + Sandro Fiore	00:15					
17:25 talk	Donatello Elia	CMCC	00:20	A HPDA-enabled environment for scalable climate data analysis			00:00 +	17:05
17:45 talk	Julian Kunkel	University of Reading	00:20	Data-Centric IO: Potential for Climate/Weather			01:00 -	16:25
18:05 talk	Jeff Durachta	NOAA GFDL	00:20	Initial Experiences with a Cluster Mounted Flash File System			06:00 -	11:45
18:25 talk	Aparna Radhakrishnan	Princeton University/NOAA GFDL	00:20	Building blocks for exascale computing at GFDL			06:00 -	12:05
18:45	Valerio Pascucci	Univ. of Utah	00:20	Data Analytics and Visualization of Massive Climate and Weather Data			08:00 -	10:25
18:45	End		03:35					

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